

Thermal Defect-Engineering of Precious Group Metal-Organic Frameworks: A Case Study on Ru/Rh-HKUST-1 Analogues

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ABSTRACT: A methodology is introduced for controlled post-synthetic thermal defect-engineering (TDE) of precious group metal-organic frameworks (PGM-MOFs). The case study is based on the Ru/Rh analogues of the archetypical structure [Cu₃(BTC)₂] (HKUST-1; BTC = 1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylate). Quantitative monitoring the TDE process and extensive characterization of the samples employing a complementary set of analytical and spectroscopic techniques reveal that the compositionally very complex TDE-MOF materials result from elimination and/or fragmentation of ancillary ligands and/or linkers. TDE involves the preferential secession of acetate ligands, intrinsically introduced via coordination modulation during synthesis, and the gradual decarboxylation of ligator sites of the framework linker BTC. Both processes lead to modified Ru/Rh paddlewheel nodes. These nodes exhibit a lowered average oxidation state and more accessible open metal centers, as deduced from surface-ligand IR spectroscopy using CO as probe and supported by DFT-based computations. The monometallic and the mixed metal PGM-MOFs systematically differ in their TDE properties and, in particular in the hydride generation ability (HGA). This latter property is an important indicator for the catalytic activity of PGM-MOFs as demonstrated by the ethylene dimerization reaction to 1-butene.

INTRODUCTION

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are unique among solid state materials in structural design and precise molecular tunability¹⁻⁴ and thus offer fascinating dimensions for potential applications.⁵⁻⁸ The very high abundance of exposed and accessible reaction centers of defined nature as well as the chemically programmable and confined coordination space of the pore structure render MOFs highly interesting for catalysis.⁹⁻¹⁴ Although reticular chemistry naturally strived for perfect compositional definition, highest crystallinity of samples and thus maximizing framework structural perfection, this paradigm is hence shifting towards also acknowledging the new opportunities that arise from defective structures, a characteristic feature of any solid state material,¹⁵ and thus to compositionally much more complex MOFs.¹⁶⁻²¹

The controlled introduction of defects – termed defect-engineering (DE) – has been recognized as valuable tool of tailoring MOF properties beyond the choice of nodes, linkers and topology.²²⁻²⁷ DEMOF design strategies can be grouped into two categories: *De novo* synthesis, for example by implementing defect generating (truncated) linkers during synthesis²⁸⁻³¹ and *post-synthetic* modifications (PSM) of pristine MOFs.^{23, 32} For example, PSM by thermal annealing (TA) beyond activation is widely used to remove chemisorbed coordination modulators to yield open metal sites (OMS) at the nodes. UiO-66 has been the prime model case for this concept and as well HKUST-1 (Cu, Ru) and UHM-3 for exploiting related linker fragmentation processes (e.g. decarboxylation).^{16, 33-36}

Figure 1: Presented in this work, thermal defect engineering (TDE) of Ru/Rh-HKUST-1 activates the materials for efficient ethylene dimerization by creating modified node defects featuring a lower average oxidation state, more accessible metal centers and M-H species as a function of the Ru/Rh composition.

The thermal annealing (TA) could thus become a very attractive and general method for DEMOF synthesis. TA targets the more or less narrow temperature window between activation (desorption of physisorbed guests)^{25, 64-66} and decomposition (collapse of the framework; carbonizing to MOF-derived materials).³⁷⁻⁴¹ However, moving from the more qualitative TA towards a truly quantitative thermal defect engineering (TDE) requires quite a conceptual step ahead in process design and the precise control of thermal PSM of MOFs.

Herein, we want to present our results on TDE of the precious group metal (PGM) based HKUST-1 (Ru, Rh) analogues as the materials of choice for our proof-of-concept study. The selection is based on the combination of high chemical, thermal and mechanical stability with defect tolerance and redox flexibility. In addition, our choice is motivated by the importance of PGMs for catalysis on an industrial scale and the lack of fundamental and systematic research on PGM-based MOFs. Among the first PGM-MOFs to be investigated in some detail were the mixed valent Ru^{II,III} and the univalent Ru^{II,II} analogues of the archetypical [Cu₃(BTC)₂] (HKUST-1; BTC = 1,3,5-benzenedicarboxylate).⁴²⁻⁴⁴ Like the parent structure, the Ru-HKUST-1 feature tetra-connected, dinuclear Ru-paddlewheel (PW) nodes. In the mixed valence Ru^{II,III} case, additional chloride (Cl) and acetate (OAc) ligands axially coordinate to the PWs and compensate for the higher oxidation state.⁴⁵ The synthesis of Ru-HKUST-1 is based on the so-called controlled secondary building unit approach (CSA) employing precursors with preformed M₂(OAc)₂ PW units. A range of PGM-HKUST-1 analogues have been obtained accordingly (M = Ru, Rh⁴³⁻⁴⁹) including mixed metal congeners with homometallic Ru^{II,III} and Rh^{II,II} nodes in varying molar ratios and doped (Cu, PGM)-HKUST-1 derivatives.⁵⁰⁻⁵² For the Ru/Rh-HKUST-1, it was found that the preparation of phase pure, crystalline and highly porous products is strongly reliant on high amounts of acetic acid (HOAc) as co-solvent.^{28, 30, 53} It acts as a coordination modulator and is retained (chemisorbed) in the final material due to very slow substitution kinetics at the PGM nodes.²³⁻²⁴ The development of an acetate-free synthesis for perfect, i.e. "defect free", compositionally simple PGM-HKUST-1 (exactly matching the empirical formula [M₃(BTC)₂] has proved to be highly demanding and this problem is still not solved.

Herein we present a comprehensive report on TDE of Ru/Rh-HKUST-1 by comparing the univalent Rh^{II,II} and mixed valence Ru^{II,III} with their mixed-metal RuRh derivatives together with the univalent Ru^{II,II} based on a complementary set of analytical techniques. We present structure-property relationships on the solid gas interactions (N₂, CO, H₂, D₂, C₂H₆, C₂H₄) and on the catalytic ethylene dimerization to 1-butene as a test reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General Information

Full experimental details regarding utilized reagents, solvents, analytical techniques (instruments) and methods are provided in the supporting information (ESI). For all prepared samples, an (X/Y) nomenclature will be used, referring to X % Rh feed fraction (incorporation confirmed by ICP-MS)⁴⁹ of the respective parental M-MOF (M-HKUST-1) and

Y % post-synthetically induced defects. Note, the value Y % refers basically to the amount of removed carboxylate ligand sites (CO₂) coordinating to the paddlewheel units of the framework. However, the details are complicated and will be discussed in the main text. An elaborate description how this empirical parameter was derived based on the analytical data is given in the supporting information.

Thermal defect engineering (TDE) was performed using a TGA-MS setup operated within an argon-filled glovebox. Volatiles were analyzed on-line with mass spectrometry (TG-MS coupling) PXRD was conducted with Cu K- α radiation in a range of 5-50° 2 θ using a Panalytical Empyrean. Analytical C and H contents were determined using a Hekatech EuroEA elemental analyzer, metal contents (Ru, Rh) were derived from TGA based metal oxide residues (assuming M₂O₃ as confirmed by PXRD) in synthetic air in accordance with ICP-MS as reported earlier.⁴⁹ Repeating units for deriving the empirical formulae were calculated using elemental contents (C, H, M) and a solver-based approach using Microsoft Excel (details see ESI). Variable temperature PXRD and FT-IR measurements were conducted with pristine Ru-, RuRh- and Rh-MOFs (0/0), (50/0) and (100/0). Sorption properties of pristine and defective samples were studied using nitrogen (N₂, 77K), ethane (C₂H₆) and ethene (C₂H₄), each 278K, 288K and 298K. DFT-based pore size distributions were determined using N₂ sorption isotherms, isosteric energies of adsorption for ethane and ethene sorption were determined using *Clausius-Clapeyron* and *Langmuir-Freundlich* equations for gas loadings in the range of 10 to 50 cm³g⁻¹. FT-IR spectra were recorded from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ using an ATR unit, Raman spectra from 20 to 2000 cm⁻¹ with 532 nm laser wavelength excitation. Variable temperature FT-IR was conducted using (0/0), (50/0), (100/0) and Ru^{II,II} samples with N₂, H₂ or D₂ gas flow. High resolution CO-probe FT-IR spectroscopy was conducted in UHV at low temperatures after treatments at different annealing temperatures for defect creation. All density functional theory (DFT) calculations performed in ORCA 4.2.0. Minnesota DFT functionals (M06 and M06L) were used with def2-TZVP basis set and RIJCOSX approximation (see Supporting information for details).

TDE-MOF Synthesis Method

Pristine samples of Ru-MOF (0%Rh), RuRh- (50%Rh) and Rh-MOF (100%Rh) and a Ru^{II,II}-MOF reference sample were prepared in solvothermal reactions following the controlled secondary building unit approach (CSA) as reported earlier.^{44, 49} After stepwise solvent exchange (H₂O, EtOH, Me₂CO, CH₂Cl₂ each twice), subsequent desolvation (activation in dynamic vacuum at 150 °C, $\approx 10^{-2}$ mbar) and basic characterization (PXRD, FTIR, N₂ adsorption), thus obtained pristine, clean MOF samples were further processed using a thermogravimetry instrument (TG) coupled with a mass spectrometer (MS). This led to the definition of thermal defect engineering protocols (TDE) and the reproducible synthesis of samples with defined defectiveness on a preparative microscale (~30 mg). TDE of the samples were performed using a TG-MS setup within a glovebox. This allowed accessibility of both, predefined weight-losses and the protection of the obtained highly reactive samples from undesired deactivation in air (e.g. uncontrolled guest sorption or oxidation). TDE-MOF sample ho-

mogeneity is ensured through a multi-step temperature program design (Figure 2) utilizing successive isothermal steps as a combination of isothermal parts and ramps with constant heating rates.⁵⁴ Weight-loss monitoring allowed for a controlled TDE between 150 °C (423 K) and 300 °C (573 K) to reproducibly yield samples of specified (Y%) defectiveness. Specifically, pre-defined analytical mass losses of 5.5 %, 10 % and 15 % (due to small molecular mass species $C_xH_yO_z$, e.g. H_2O , CO , CO_2 , $H_2C=C=O$) were targeted to yield three series of samples for each pristine MOF of the study. On the basis of elemental analysis and thereof derived sum formulae, different quantitative defect descriptors (%) were calculated depending on the whole organic fraction, removed carboxylate ligator sites (CO_2) and finally including Cl ligands. An overview is provided in Table S3. Using the above-mentioned nomenclature, the samples are denoted 10%, 20% and 30% defectiveness in the following. However, note, this descriptor is simplified to facilitate sample denomination. Details are discussed in the main text and the ESI.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Concept of study and leading questions

Previous work on various kinds of defect engineered and/or hydrogen-pretreated Ru-HKUST-1⁵⁵ revealed a characteristic boost of the catalytic activity in several test reactions such as the *Meerwein-Ponndorf-Verley* hydride transfer, in the isomerization of allylic alcohols to saturated ketones and in selective ethene dimerization to 1-butene.^{30, 56} These studies raised a number of questions: What is the role of the high amount of residual (chemisorbed) acetate and chloride ligands in the pristine Ru-MOF samples and the fate of these species during activation and defect engineering? How are Ru-H species formed? How is the metal oxidation state affected during TDE and how does this correlate with the catalytic activity? To which extent a transfer of findings is possible from Ru to Rh? Can we draw more general conclusions on TDE of MOFs using the above defined model systems as a study case? Previous works on thermal treatments of MOFs typically lack precise analytical monitoring of the process and have mainly been limited to MOF-5 and UiO-66 (and related systems), the investigation of the activation parameters⁵⁷ and removing loosely bound framework components, including coordination modulators.^{16, 33-34} Our study goes beyond this previous work. It is guided by the idea of targeting controlled linker fragmentation (e.g. decarboxylation) at the temperature window between activation and framework collapse. Since PGM-HKUST-1 analogues are thermally very robust and at the same time contain catalytically very versatile and redox-active metal centers, we selected them for this detailed case study.

Sample Synthesis, TDE based on TG-MS Data

Based on the previous report on thermal treatment of Ru-HKUST-1,⁶² we developed a procedure to reproducibly access different stages of defectiveness in the MOF samples (experimental part, see also ESI). From the TG-MS data of the carefully activated samples in the temperature window between 150 and 300 °C the following information is obtained. For all samples, H_2O , CO and CO_2 , are observed as major elimination species peaking on each temperature increase (Figures S1-2). Additional species, in particular ketene ($H_2C=C=O$) and other

Figure 2: Weight loss profiles and the temperature program for PGM-MOF thermal defect engineering (TDE). The plateau at 150 °C between min 20 and 40 (vertical highlighted area) indicates complete removal of weakly physisorbed species and guests (solvents). The dashed vertical line indicates the point of weight-referencing (activated, “clean” sample). The dashed horizontal lines indicate the targeted weight-loss for 10%, 20% and 30% defectiveness. For experimental details see ESI.

small $C_xH_yO_z$ fragments (C_3H , $C_2H_4O_2$, $C_2H_2O_3$) are detected. The comparison with literature data on the thermal properties of densely packed (stacked metal sites) metal carboxylates suggests similar decomposition mechanisms taking place in open, highly porous (isolated metal sites), i.e. MOFs studied herein.⁵⁸ In contrast to these species, acetate elimination ($m/z = 60$) takes place at 250°C almost quantitatively without detectable peaks at lower or higher temperatures. This suggests a preferred removal of acetate (both monodentate and bridging) over complete BTC elimination or partial BTC ligator site decarboxylation which takes places mostly at higher temperatures. A differentiation between eliminated monodentate (axial) and bridging (equatorial) acetates is not substantiated on a quantitative basis (for qualitative assignments, CO-SLIR and Raman data discussed below and Table S2). However, chemical intuition suggests removal of $OAc_{(axial)} > OAc_{(eq)} > BTC_{(fragmentation)}$ according to hapticity (monodentate vs bridging) and binding properties (with or without framework incorporation / dative or covalent bond). Upon temperature increase to 250°C, detection of trace amounts of ^{35}Cl in Ru-containing samples indicates removal of Cl-species from the mixed-valent $Ru^{II,III}$ nodes. However, as discussed later, elemental analysis revealed the Cl content to be mostly unaffected. Traces of Cl are potentially released in the form of HCl. From a TGA-MS experiment with consecutive treatment in N_2 and H_2 atmosphere (Figure S3) we conclude that Cl – although reluctant to be removed in inert atmosphere (N_2) – readily forms HCl ($m/z = 35$) when TDE is conducted in H_2 atmosphere and thereby generates M-H species (detected by FT-IR, *vide infra*). Upon TDE the samples darkened, especially the bright green 100% Rh sample. This can indicate formation of modified PWs and/or of metal nanoparticles. Rh-MOF appears to have a slightly higher thermal stability as defect generation requires more time or higher temperatures as compared to Ru-MOF.

Composition and Definition of Defectiveness

TGA allows for quantification of the metal oxide residues (according to ref.⁴⁹) and thus the determination of the total metal content (M_{tot}) of each sample. With increasing loss of small $C_xH_yO_z$ components (as described above) the “defectiveness” is rising, and consequently all samples exhibit rising M_{tot} as well (Table 1). This empirical parameter “defectiveness” can

Table 1: Elemental contents, calculated sum formulae, derived metal charges and related N₂ surface areas.

Sample	Found C/H/Cl/M _{tot} content [wt-%]	Ascertained sum formula	Mean metal charge	BET surface area	
				[m ² g ⁻¹]	[m ² mmol ⁻¹]
Rh-BTC	(100/0)	[Rh ₃ (BTC) _{1.61} (OAc) _{1.89}]	+2.24	1360	1025
	(100/10)	[Rh ₃ (BTC) _{1.22} (IPA) _{0.39} (OAc) _{1.34}]	+1.92	1340	943
	(100/20)	[Rh ₃ (BTC) _{0.86} (IPA) _{0.74} (OAc) _{1.01}]	+1.70	1424	954
	(100/30)	[Rh ₃ (BTC) _{0.61} (IPA) _{0.99} (OAc) _{0.64}]	+1.49	1274	812
RuRh-BTC	(50/0)	[Ru _{1.44} Rh _{1.56} (BTC) _{1.52} (OAc) _{2.69} Cl _{0.3}]	+2.53	1211	958
	(50/10)	[Ru _{1.44} Rh _{1.56} (BTC) _{1.36} (IPA) _{0.57} (OAc) _{1.03} Cl _{0.3}]	+2.19	n.d.	n.d.
	(50/20)	[Ru _{1.44} Rh _{1.56} (BTC) _{0.64} (IPA) _{1.27} (OAc) _{0.64} Cl _{0.3}]	+1.80	n.d.	n.d.
	(50/30)	[Ru _{1.44} Rh _{1.56} (BTC) _{0.54} (IPA) _{1.27} (OAc) _{0.52} Cl _{0.3}]	+1.66	n.d.	n.d.
Ru-BTC	(0/0)	[Ru ₃ (BTC) _{1.89} (OAc) _{1.55} Cl _{0.7}]	+2.64	1018	825
	(0/10)	[Ru ₃ (BTC) _{0.56} (IPA) _{1.32} (OAc) _{1.55} Cl _{0.65}]	+2.18	1065	801
	(0/20)	[Ru ₃ (BTC) _{0.82} (IPA) _{1.44} (OAc) ₀ Cl _{0.61}]	+1.97	1034	755
	(0/30)	[Ru ₃ (BTC) _{1.12} (IPA) _{0.76} (OAc) _{0.24} Cl _{0.57}]	+1.90	1173	816
	Ru ^{II,III}	[Ru ₃ (BTC) _{1.32} (OAc) _{2.22}]	+2.06	1493	1056

Figure 3: Correlation of hydrogen content (left) and calculated mean metal charge (right) with sample defectiveness (see definition 1 in ESI). Calculation assuming quantitatively deprotonated carboxylates (OAc, IPA, BTC).

be quantitatively defined in various ways depending on the removed fraction of (a) the total organic content ($C_wH_xO_yCl_z$), (b) the total removed ligands (CH_3CO_2 , CO_2 and Cl) or (c) particularly referring to the removed carboxylate ligand sites (CO_2). For reasons of simplicity and to level the slight differences between these different viewpoints, the TDE samples are thus denoted as 10%, 20% and 30% defectiveness, respectively. Detailed definitions for “defectiveness” and related quantitative defect amounts (Table S3) are provided in the ESI. The derived M_{tot} were complemented by analytical C, H, Cl elemental analysis (EA) providing the basis for non-linear solver-assisted empirical sum formulae calculations. As shown previously, C, H and M contents serve a sufficient basis for a reliable sum formulae calculation utilizing a tailored solver approach.⁴⁹ Note, however, unfortunately a quantitative acid digestion (even in aqua regia) is not possible with these samples. Thus, a reliable quantitative determination of organic components, e.g. BTC, IPA, OAc proved not sufficiently reliable by HPLC or NMR analysis.⁴⁹ Defining OAc and

BTC as the exclusive organic framework components, the applied solver provides good and reproducible fitting results for the pristine PGM-MOFs. For the TDE-MOF samples, we nevertheless have to make assumptions for the composition based on the combined analytical and spectroscopic evidences. Thus, the scope of plausible framework components is complemented by isophthalate (IPA) as decarboxylation product from BTC. This reasoning is in line with existing literature.⁵⁹⁻⁶⁰ Both, the experimentally found hydrogen content as well as the derived (formal) mean metal charges correlate well with increasing sample “defectiveness” defined by TGA as can be seen in Figure 3. Taking into account that pristine Ru- and Rh-MOFs should have mean (formal) metal charges of 2.5 and 2.0, the herein obtained values are in good agreement with the expected outcome. A differentiation between axially and equatorially (bridging) bound acetates is shown for pristine MOFs in Table S2. Neither hydrides, nor hydroxides nor acidic protons were considered (due to the absence of quantification methods) in the calculation of the formal mean metal charges. Thus, there is some intrinsic uncertainty of the assumed sum formulae. As reported earlier, XPS does not allow unambiguous quantification and assignments of metal oxidation states in these PGM-MOFs. Alternatives to the herein chosen approach (EA-based solver and CO-probe FT-IR spectroscopy as discussed below) to access metal oxidation states are sophisticated synchrotron techniques like the X-ray absorption near-edge structure spectroscopy (XANES). Since the high energy X-rays particularly required for Ru and Rh are limited to just a few facilities worldwide, such synchrotron-based techniques were not available for this study.⁴⁹

All the obtained TDE-MOF samples were then characterized by standard TGA. The resulting graphs are depicted in Figure S9-S11. A correlation between defectiveness and thermal stability can be deduced. The slightly decreasing characteristic decomposition temperatures (above 250 °C) are perfectly aligned with the materials rising defectiveness. Intuitively,

any removal of stabilizing linkers creates an ever more destabilized structure. However, we emphasize that the decrease of thermal stability in DE-Cu-HKUST-1 (de novo synthesis by defect generating linkers) is much more pronounced with rising defectiveness as compared to TDE-PGM-HKUST-1 studied herein.³¹

TDE-MOFs: Structure and Stability

Variable temperature programmed XRD data (VT-XRD) of the three pristine Ru/Rh-MOF samples 100%Rh, 50%Rh and 0%Rh are displayed in Figure 4. All three samples preserve their structure until amorphization between 350°C and 400°C, with Ru-MOF (0%Rh) showing the highest thermal stability. Amorphization occurs without any intermediate phase transformation for all samples. On first glance, this is inconsistent with TGA-based results, from which Rh-BTC seems slightly more stable. As amorphization in general depends on the thermal stability, we primarily attribute these findings to differences in the pristine defect content and crystallite sizes.⁶¹⁻⁶² The individual PXRD measurements of all synthesized, still crystalline TDE-MOFs indicate retention of the HKUST-1 analogous structure, as can be seen in Figures S4 and S5. The 100%Rh sample treated up to 250 °C features broad reflections and in this case, Rh-NP formation ($41.1^\circ 2\theta$) correlates with the defect amount which is already visible in the (100/10) sample.

Sorption Properties

Nitrogen Sorption

For all samples, nitrogen ad- and desorption follows a reversible Type I (b) isotherm. Generally, the gravimetric N₂ surface areas of TDE-MOFs increase with respect to the pristine MOFs as can be seen in Table 1 and Figure 5. The increase in gravimetric surface area is more pronounced in Ru-based materials. Transformed into molar values, a decrease can be observed which is attributed to the removal of framework components during TDE and thus lower typical molar mass of the respective repeating units. The still high and preserved porosity is in accordance with predominantly preserved framework structures as found through crystallographic and spectroscopic means. All TDE-MOFs exhibit a successively reduced number of micropores of $\sim 7-8$ Å to the benefit of larger (meso) pores (>15 Å) (see the emerging hysteresis in the plateaus of the TDE isotherms and their PSD plots in Figure 5 and also Figure S16-S19), which is assigned to linker fragmentation via decarboxylation (BTC \rightarrow IPA) upon TDE. Pristine mixed valence Ru^{II,III}-MOF, comprising axial ligands (Cl, OAc), features additional pores: A medium-sized micropore of ~ 9 Å is present. In HKUST-1-type frameworks, three different pores occur: A small one (further called pore A) with ~ 8 Å and two degenerate pores with ~ 10 Å size (further called pore B and C). However, the axial positions of the PWs pointing only into one (pore B) of these degenerate pores. Thus, the presence of axial ligands in mixed-valent Ru^{II,III}-HKUST-1 causes this pore B to be reduced to ~ 9 Å, abolishing the degeneration. Upon TDE, axial acetate ligands seem to be removed preferentially as aforementioned medium-sized micropore cannot be observed in TDE-Ru-MOFs anymore. As reported earlier, the synthesis procedure for the Ru^{II,III}-MOF provides a rather defective material also featuring mesopores (see Figure 5).⁴⁴

Figure 4: VT-XRD pattern contour plots of PGM-MOFs. Left: 100%Rh-, middle: 50%Rh-, right: 0%Rh-sample. Upon higher temperatures new reflections indicate NP formation. PXRD pattern of pristine MOFs at ambient temperature are shown on top of each contour plot. Note: Additional lines from Al sample holder become visible.

Figure 5: Top: Nitrogen sorption isotherms recorded at 77K. Closed symbols represent adsorption, open symbols desorption branches. Bottom: Incremental pore volumes displaying the DFT-derived pore size distribution assuming cylindrical pores on oxide surfaces. Left: 0%Rh series; right: 100%Rh series. TDE leads to an increase in gas uptake and merging of small pores into larger mesopores (see pores > 15 Å).

Figure 6: Isothermic energy of adsorption for ethane derived from sorption isotherms. Left: Ru-based MOFs; right: Rh-based MOFs. No energetic differences can be observed for TDE-MOFs. Energies of adsorption slightly decrease upon higher loadings. For Rh-TDE-MOFs EoA increase upon TDE peaking in (100/20).

Ethane and Ethene Sorption

Ethane (C_2H_6) and ethene (C_2H_4) sorption experiments were performed aiming for correlations with the observed differences of the TDE-MOFs in ethene dimerization activity (see below). For ideal, reversible sorption on innocent hosts, adsorbed gas amounts should decrease with higher sorption temperatures. With isotherms recorded at different temperatures (here 278, 288 and 298K), the isosteric Energy of Adsorption (EoA) can be determined. For the saturated hydrocarbon ethane, the trends appear as expected and (gravimetric) sorption capacities increase with defectiveness (Figure S22-27, Table S3). In line with the N_2 -based results, the sample (100/20) has the highest ethane uptake within the Rh series. Within the Ru series the uptake also increases with defectiveness and the $Ru^{II,III}$ sample allows the highest uptake. Desorption of ethane is quantitative for all samples suggesting fully reversible sorption processes. Derived EoAs for ethane can be seen in Figure 6. Ru-based TDE-MOFs have only subtle differences in ethane sorption energies which decrease with higher loadings (left graph) suggesting preferred adsorption sites as also observed for Cu-HKSUT-1.⁶³ Interestingly, the univalent Ru-MOF features lower EoA ($\approx 25 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) than mixed-valent Ru-MOF ($\approx 30 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). Temperature-induced removal of axially bound OAc seem to render the pore environment less lipophilic. In contrast, on Rh samples, ethane EoAs are independent from the loading but generally increase upon TDE from $\approx 30 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in pristine Rh-MOF up to $\approx 40 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in (100/20) sample (right graph).

The ethene (C_2H_4) sorption isotherms are depicted in Figures S28-S29. Strong hysteresis between adsorption and desorption branches as well as significant amounts of irreversibly adsorbed species (further called residues) are observed most predominantly for TDE-MOFs. Such behaviour of inversed

temperature trends to what was anticipated has been rarely reported in MOF literature so far.⁶⁴⁻⁶⁵ These other data were assigned to pore window blocking at low temperatures. Herein, however, we assign our data to a partial chemisorption of ethene (e.g. to some chemical reactivity at the nodes). This correlates with temperature dependence and counteracts the anticipated physisorption behaviour inverting the expected trend. Unfortunately, this effect prevents meaningful EoA calculations for comparison. Nevertheless, some additional conclusions can be drawn from ethene sorption isotherms. Based on the molar uptake and amount of residues ($\text{mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}_{\text{MOF}}$), we estimated the number of adsorbed ethene molecules per paddlewheel unit. Correlation of ethene uptakes and residues with sorption temperature and sample defectiveness were visualized in contour plots displayed in Figure 7. Strong chemisorption of ethene occurs on Ru-MOF and on Rh-MOF (most certainly at OMS: see Figure S20-S21 for N_2 isotherms and PSDs after repeated ethene sorption according to literature reports⁶⁶⁻⁶⁷). However, some additional reactivity seems to be exclusive for Ru-based MOFs. This can be concluded from the significantly increased amount of residues at the highest sorption temperature (see Table S4-S5). Drastically increased uptake and residues for the most defective (0/30) Ru-MOF sample suggests the highest reactivity towards ethene in this series. In line with the postulated TDE-induced metal reduction to $Ru^{\delta+}$ species (see below), the $Ru^{II,III}$ reference sample (see the band on top of the Ru residue contour map in Figure 7) perfectly follows the same temperature dependence. This is in line with the hydride generating ability (HGA) of Ru-MOF discussed later (see IR spectra in Figure 8, bottom left graph) being a prerequisite for ethene dimerization (or oligomerization) reactivity.

To summarize sorption properties, TDE does not critically affect the porous structure of the pristine MOFs, but partial linker fragmentation (decarboxylation $BTC \rightarrow IPA + CO_2$) and/or removal ($OAc \rightarrow CO/CO_2/C_xH_yO_z$) supports a mesopore formation in all materials. For ethane energy of adsorption is $\approx 30 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for Ru-MOFs irrespective of their defectiveness while defects in Rh-MOFs clearly increase EoAs up to $\approx 40 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Typical for non-reactive sorbents, lower sorption temperatures allow higher gas uptakes for ethane.

There is strong **ethene uptake** for Ru-MOF and Rh-MOF rather irrespective of both the temperature and defectiveness peaking at the $Ru^{II,III}$ sample. Both metals obviously bind ethene strongly. Thus, **ethene residues** remain bound in the materials after desorption. In Rh-MOFs, roughly one molecule ethene per PW remains bound rather independent from sorption temperature and sample defectiveness. Oppositely, defective Ru-MOFs and particularly their univalent $Ru^{II,III}$ analogue trap increasing amounts of ethene at higher temperatures indicating a **reactive sorption** (chemisorption). Residues exceeding one molecule ethene bound per PW support the postulated reduction and generation of more OMS upon TDE.

Figure 7: Contour plots of ethylene sorption: Left side: Ru; right side: Rh-MOFs. Top row: Uptake in molecules per PW. Bottom row: Residue in molecules per PW. The dashed isoline represents the threshold of one molecule per PW. A different visualization is shown in Figure S30-31.

Figure 8: Top: FT-IR spectra of selected TDE-MOF and Ru^{II,III} samples revealing the general bonding similarity. Bottom: Zoom-ins of highlighted regions for Ru-MOF samples. Left: Emerging Ru-H (dashed lines: Ru²⁺-H, compact lines: Ru^{δ+}-H and Ru-CO (bold line) bands upon TDE. Intensities are scaled by a factor of 3. Right: blue shift of $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ suggests axial acetate removal and reduction towards Ru^{II,III} nodes upon TDE.

Vibrational Spectroscopy

To gain comprehensive insights into the bonding situation both FT-IR and Raman spectroscopy were applied (including CO as a probe molecule) and further supported by computational calculations on model molecules allowing assignment of individual vibration modes (see Table S6).

Almost identical FT-IR spectra support the overall isostructurality of all samples as shown in Figure 8 (top graph). Significant changes, however, occur upon TDE, particularly with Ru-MOF (0%Rh samples). Generally, in carboxylate-based coordination compounds, the valence modes of COO are very sensitive towards changes at the metal center due to their direct bonds and close vicinities.⁶⁸ Here, a hypochromic shift of $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ of mixed-valent Ru^{II,III}-MOF results in a band shape and position identical to the univalent 100%Rh and the Ru^{II,III} reference sample being displayed in the bottom right graph in Figure 8. This is explained by the hypothesis of a thermally induced metal reduction of the mixed valence Ru^{II,III} to the

univalent Ru^{II,III} as a consequence of axial ligand removal. As the chloride content of the Ru-containing samples does not change significantly, axial acetate must be preferentially removed. This is in accordance with existing literature on isolated dimeric Ru tetra- and pentacarboxylate complexes.⁶⁹⁻⁷⁰ Low-intensity signals resulting from weakly bound carboxylates ($\approx 1687 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) mainly occur in the (50/0) and (100/0) samples and disappear upon TDE.⁷¹⁻⁷⁴

In line with FT-IR spectra of the whole series, recorded Raman spectra support the removal of axial ligands and decarboxylation (see Figure S35-S37 and Table S7). The spectra coincide for most of the signals throughout the series of samples. Nevertheless, three characteristic effects can be observed: 1) Vibration modes attributed to axial ligands present in Ru containing samples mainly disappear in the course of TDE. The $\nu(\text{Ru-Cl})$ bands at 276 cm^{-1} exhibit only slightly decreased intensity, while $\nu(\text{Ru-OAc}_{axial})$ at 324 cm^{-1} almost completely disappears. 2) Weakly bound or free carboxylates are readily removed by TDE from 100%Rh sample, as indicated by the disappearing signal at 1688 cm^{-1} . The broadening of the band attributed to $\nu_s(\text{C=C})_{arom}$ (at 1606 cm^{-1}) suggests a modification of the aromatic scaffold which might be caused by the assumed linker decarboxylation, thus representing the increasing abundance of IPA with respect to the parent BTC linker. This supports the validity of the applied solver approach including IPA as potential framework constituent.

Hydride Generating Ability (HGA)

Upon TDE, H-Ru (hydride) species can be identified according to emerging bands ranging from 2100 to 1950 cm^{-1} .⁷⁵ As indicated in the bottom left graph in Figure 8, H-Ru²⁺ (dashed lines at 2074 and 2059 cm^{-1}) emerge at an early stage of defect formation (samples (0/10) and (0/20)) while reduced site H-Ru^{δ+} preferentially emerge in highly defective samples. The signal assignment is based on literature information.^{30,56} The observation of hydrides is remarkable since TDE is performed in inert atmosphere without any supply of H₂ gas. However, in line with the literature, an alternative thermal treatment at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in H₂ atmosphere yields identical Ru-H species. As demonstrated previously, the formation of these metal hydrides appears to be a key requisite for ethene dimerization reactivity and can enhance hydride transfer reactions.^{55-56,76} It remains unclear at this level of our study how the mechanism for metal hydride formation proceeds under otherwise inert conditions. We assume the decomposition of hydrogen containing framework components (OAc, BTC) by radical mechanisms and/or by concerted C-H activation and potential H-transfer to the metal nodes. Interestingly, such species are barely visible in Rh-based TDE-MOFs revealing significant differences in the metal-based HGA (see Figures S32-34). This is supported by very weak rhodium hydride signals even after H₂ or D₂ treatment (see Figure S38-39) and a neglectable ethene dimerization activity as will be discussed later.

To gain deeper insights into the differences of the applied materials, we utilized more elaborate IR studies using variable temperatures and CO probing at low temperatures under UHV conditions which are part of discussion in the next chapter.

Figure 9: UHV-FTIRS data obtained after CO adsorption (0.01 mbar) on different pristine and TDE-PGM-MOFs at 105 K. Before CO adsorption, the samples were preheated at the indicated temperatures (373 K to 563 K) for in-situ defect generation. a) Ru-MOF (0 % Rh); b) Rh-MOF (100 % Rh); c) Ru/Rh-MOF (50 % Rh).

CO Probe FT-IR Spectroscopy

The controlled introduction of defects in the MOFs via TDE was monitored by CO-SLIR (surface-ligand IR spectroscopy) approach⁷⁷ highly sensitive to the oxidation states and coordination environments of metal atoms. Figure 9 shows the corresponding IR results for different TDE-MOFs after exposure to CO recorded at 105 K. Clearly, a number of distinctly different bands are observed. On the basis of previous work²⁸ and the present new findings, these characteristic bands are assigned in Table 2.

The mixed-valent, pristine (activated) Ru-MOF is dominated by two characteristic CO bands at 2171 cm^{-1} (OC-Ru³⁺) and 2135 cm^{-1} (OC-Ru²⁺), which have been reported previously.²⁸ The TDE of Ru-MOF at elevated temperatures leads to the appearance of two new low-frequency peaks at 2040 and 1996 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to OC-Ru ^{δ +} species (CO bound to reduced electron-rich Ru centers) with lower Ru coordination numbers. This conclusion is in line with the observation of similar frequencies reported for Ru-OMS of DE-Ru- HKUST-1 prepared by the mixed-linker approach.^{29-30,53} The formation of Ru ^{δ +} defects in TDE-Ru-MOF samples is further accompanied by a slight red-shift of the OC-Ru²⁺ bands from 2135 to 2122 cm^{-1} . This feature is assigned to the structural and electronic modifications of Ru-dimer nodes caused by the thermal decarboxylation. This is in line with the spectrum of the univalent Ru^{II} sample which already in its pristine state seems to be dominated by a related and rather defective structure (see sorption data in Figure 5 and Figure S45). As shown in

Figure 9a, the defect-related CO bands gain substantial intensity only after annealing the sample to temperatures at or higher than 480 K. The situation is thus similar to Cu-based UHM-3³⁶ and HKUST-1.^{35,78}

Table 2: CO FT-IR probe spectroscopy. Assignment of bands for PGM-MOF samples including Cu-HKUST-1 and UHM-3 literature values.

Sample	Band (cm^{-1})	Assignment
Ru-MOF	2171	Ru ³⁺ -CO
	2135-2122	Ru ²⁺ -CO
	2040, 1996	Ru ^{δ+} -CO
Rh-MOF	2113	Rh ²⁺ -CO
	2072	Rh ¹⁺ -CO
RuRh-MOF	2168	Ru ³⁺ -CO
	2116	Rh ²⁺ -CO
	2035, 1994	Ru ^{δ+} -CO
Cu-HKUST-1 ³⁵	2179	Cu ²⁺ -CO
	2156*	Cu ⁺ -(CO) ₂
	2121	Cu ⁺ -CO
UHM-3 ³⁶	2175	Cu ²⁺ -CO
	2153	Unclear**
	2118	Cu ⁺ -CO

*putative assignment, **we assume Cu⁺(CO)₂ similar to Lit³⁵.

However, in these different MOFs, TDE was found to occur at lower temperatures (370 – 420 K). Thus, Ru^{II,III}-HKUST-1 reveals a higher thermal stability as compared to the Cu-PW based analogues.³⁵⁻³⁶ The CO-SLIR data for the pristine Rh-HKUST-1 exhibits one intense IR band at 2113 cm⁻¹ (Figure 9b), which is attributed to a OC-Rh²⁺ species. We assign the weak shoulder at 2072 cm⁻¹ to a small amount of reduced OC-Rh¹⁺ defect sites. The spectral evolution along with the annealing to higher temperatures reveals that Rh^{II,III}-MOF is slightly more stable (a significant decrease of the OC-Rh²⁺ band occurs at T > 540 K) than the Ru^{II,III}-MOF, which is in excellent agreement with the TGA-based data (see Figure 2 & S9-11). Furthermore, the IR signal at 2153 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of a geminal dicarbonyl species (OC)₂Rh¹⁺, indicating a reduced Rh¹⁺ site being two-fold coordinatively unsaturated.³¹

Upon further heating and annealing above 560 K a broad feature appears at about 2000-2060 cm⁻¹. Such low vibrational frequencies suggest the presence of (uncharged) metal Rh nanoparticles resulting from a progressive thermal decomposition of the MOF framework. This is in line with PXRD data (Figure S5-6).

The pristine RuRh-MOF (50%Rh) is characterized by two dominating IR bands at 2168 and 2116 cm⁻¹ originating from OC-Ru³⁺ and OC-Rh²⁺ species, respectively (Figure 9c). As observed and discussed earlier, the mixed-metal sample presumably comprises a statistic mixture of monometallic PWs rather than mixed-metal PWs.⁴⁹ The band assignment is further supported by temperature-dependent CO-SLIR. As shown in Figure S44, CO desorbs from Ru³⁺ sites already at about 130 K, while for Rh²⁺ and Rh¹⁺ sites substantially higher desorption temperatures (above 320 K) are observed. We explain this by stronger bonds, resulting from additional charge available for π -backdonation in relation to OC-Ru³⁺ as confirmed by DFT calculations (see Table 3). For the TDE-MOFs heated to elevated temperatures (c), we clearly see two additional vibrations at 2035 and 1994 cm⁻¹, demonstrating the creation of reduced Ru⁶⁺ defects. These peaks dominate only after heating to T > 520 K, revealing a higher thermal stability of bimetallic RuRh-MOFs relative to the monometallic Ru^{II,III} analogue.

We have further carried out DFT calculations to gain deeper insights into the interaction of CO with pristine and TDE-Rh-MOFs. Figure 10 shows the DFT-optimized atomic structures of various CO species bound to intact Rh²⁺/Rh²⁺ as well as reduced Rh⁺/Rh²⁺ dimers. The corresponding CO stretching frequencies and binding energies are summarized in Table 3 (see ESI for details). Overall, there is good agreement between the computed and experimental results (see Table 2). We note that in the case of reduced Rh⁺/Rh²⁺ paddlewheels, the adsorption of two CO molecules (one CO at each of the two Rh cations) leads to a blue-shift in frequency (21 cm⁻¹) compared to that of the one CO structure (Figure 10). This is attributed to the electronic redistribution of the reduced Rh dimers along with the second CO adsorption. Furthermore, computations reveal that the adsorption of CO on Rh⁺/Rh²⁺ defects can stabilize the low-spin state of the system. Accordingly, CO binds stronger to Rh⁺/Rh²⁺ than to pristine paddlewheels (Table 3), in line with the temperature-dependent IR observation (Figure S44).

Figure 10: DFT-optimized atomic structures of CO adsorption on pristine and defect-engineered Rh-PWs. Carbon – yellow, Oxygen – pink, hydrogen – blue, rhodium – grey.

Table 3. Computed binding energies (E_{ads}) and vibrational frequencies (ν_{CO}) of CO adsorbed on Rh-PWs.

System	E_{ads} (kJ/mol)	ν_{CO} (cm ⁻¹)* (shift from gas CO)
Gas CO		2143
Pristine-CO	97	2096 (-47)
Pristine-2CO	63	2097 (-46)
Defect-CO	224	2044 (-99)
Defect-2CO	203	2065 (-78)

*scaled with respect to gas CO

Figure 11: Ratio of the integrated band areas for Rh-CO (**a**) and the two bands for Ru-CO (**b1** and **b2**) to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})_{\text{arom}}$ as a function of desorption temperature in N₂. MOF catalysts were pretreated at 150 °C in N₂ and CO adsorbed at 30 °C. The mixed-valent Ru-BTC is indicated with black (150 °C N₂ pretreatment) and red (300 °C N₂ pretreatment simulating the (0/30) sample), univalent Ru^{II,III} with blue data points. The data indicates labile CO binding to Rh but strong interactions with Ru sites and increasing OMS. The increase in **b1** (red line) suggests a preferred removal of axial over equatorial acetate.

In addition, CO sorption experiments were conducted at higher temperatures and at ambient pressure (see desorption graphs in Figure 11). The binding of CO at OMS was examined after CO adsorption at room temperature and its controlled desorption up to 150 °C. Thus, Figure 11 shows the ratios of the integrated band areas for Rh (**a**: 2083-2132 cm⁻¹) and for Ru (**b1**: 2049-2099 cm⁻¹ and **b2**: 1995-2033 cm⁻¹) as a function of the area of the samples' C=C band (~ 1390 cm⁻¹). All individual FTIR spectra are provided in the ESI (Figure S40-43). The strong binding of CO onto Ru sites, either in Ru^{II,III} or Ru^{II,II}, as compared to Rh sites becomes evident with the slope for increasing desorption temperatures.

Compared to the pristine Ru-MOF (treated at 150 °C, 10 min, black data points), a short pretreatment at 300 °C (10 min, red data points) roughly doubles the intensity of CO band **b1** which is in accordance with the observation that the number of OMS also roughly doubles (see TGA-based CO titration experiment displayed in Figure S12-15 and Table S1). Interestingly, the CO band **b2** which can be assigned to partially reduced, defective Ru^{δ+} sites does not increase with the (short-time) thermal treatment of mixed-valent Ru-MOF but merely shows a strong increase for the univalent Ru^{II,III} sample. With respect to the band assignments discussed before, we conclude a preferred removal of axial over equatorial (bridging) acetates first giving more Ru²⁺ sites prior to the formation of defective Ru^{δ+} sites. Thus, we assume the aforementioned order of ligand removal / fragmentation: OAc_(axial) > OAc_(eq) > BTC_(fragmentation) which is also consistent with the trends observed for ν_{as}(COO) as highlighted in Figure 8 (IR, bottom right graph). The different material properties with respect to metal, oxidation state and their manipulation using the controlled TDE render these materials interesting for catalysis, as detailed below.

Catalytic Ethene Dimerization

As outlined in the previous subchapter, the HGA in the TDE-MOFs and their relevance in catalysis was placed under scrutiny using ethene dimerization to 1-butene as a probe reaction. Samples were thermally treated in N₂ for defect generation and in-situ metal hydride formation prior to ethene dimerization. Ru-based MOF samples were treated under 300 °C (N₂) and intrinsic Ru-H formation takes place at this condition, however the HGA at Rh sites required additional treatment under hydrogen. We used D₂ for unambiguous detection of such hydride formation and indeed observed a second band assigned to Rh-D. Figure 12 shows ethene dimerization turnover frequencies (TOF, per total metal, M_{tot}) as a function of the Ru content in the TDE-MOF samples at 50 °C and 5 bar ethene. Such conditions enable a correct catalyst comparison under gaseous conditions and avoid different solvation phenomena in catalysis via intrapore condensation.⁵⁶ As observed in the linear trend of TOF values, the 100 %Rh-MOF shows much less activity for C–C coupling reactions into ethene dimers even after the additional hydride formation with H₂/D₂. This is despite of the more accessible univalent Rh nodes as a consequence of absent axial chloride or acetates compared to the mixed-valent Ru nodes. With increasing Ru content, the PGM-MOFs are much more catalytically active. This is in accordance with the trends seen in the hydride generating ability (HGA) upon TDE.

Such differences between Ru-MOF and Rh-MOF become also evident when the Ru oxidation states are modified by TDE. After thermal treatment at 300 °C in N₂, the TDE-Ru^{II,III}-MOF catalyst shows about four times higher activity in ethene dimerization than mixed-valent pristine Ru^{II,III}-MOF and is thus superior to the previously reported Ru-based MOF catalysts under the same reaction conditions.⁵⁶ These results confirm the relevance of the metal choice, its hydride generating ability (HGA) upon TDE and the oxidation state. TDE yields lower average Ru oxidation states if starting out with the univalent Ru^{II,III}-MOF as compared to the mixed-valence Ru^{II,III}-MOF. In addition, the TOF values as a function of time-on-stream (Figure 12b) show a pronounced induction period for Ru^{II,III} in

Figure 12: a) Ethene dimerization turnover frequency (TOF) per total metal per hour as a function of Ru content at 5 bar and 50 °C; b) TOF as a function of time-on-stream. Besides Rh-BTC, Ru-BTC, Ru^{II,III}-BTC and the 50% Rh-sample, a RuRh (90:10)-BTC sample (10 % Rh) was investigated.

contact with ethylene at 5 bar (which has been reported for Ru-MOF earlier⁵⁶). This can be attributed to the enhanced HGA in ethene stream even at 50 °C. Once at maximum TOF values, however, the activity for Ru^{II,III} shows a steady decay, attributed to the progressive deposition of larger oligomers. However, since all MOF catalysts show a 100% selectivity to 1-butene (within the detection limits), these oligomers must be formed in trace amounts. As reported earlier,⁵⁶ higher ethene pressures leading to intrapore solvation phenomena can inhibit these oligomers and thus should avoid such a progressive deactivation. A comparison between the catalytic performance of this and previous works is provided in Table S11.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the present study demonstrates a methodology for post-synthetic thermal defect-engineering (TDE) used to systematically access well defined precious group metal (PGM) TDE-MOFs (Ru/Rh-HKUST-1 analogues). Characterization with a complementary set of analytical techniques (VT-PXRD, FT-IR, Raman, TGA, EA, N₂, C₂H₆ and C₂H₄ physisorption and CO-probe FT-IR spectroscopy in UHV) shows that these compositionally very complex materials undergo successive reduction of the PGM centers at the dimeric metal nodes by ligand/linker removal or fragmentation upon TDE (a set of the putative defective (modified) PW structures is provided in Scheme S1-2). This can occur via complete removal of modulator-based acetate ligands or through decarboxylation of framework linkers (BTC → IPA). Both processes generate more open and partially reduced metal sites, thus the average oxidation state of the PGM paddlewheel nodes is lowered as seen by CO-SLIR analysis and related DFT-based computations. In the mixed-valent Ru^{II,III}-HKUST-1 case, the additional axial acetate or chloride ligand accounting for the higher charge strongly impacts the occurring reduction process. While axial acetates are readily removed, the reduction of metal nodes comprising chloride counterions requires harsher conditions. A remarkable hydride generating ability (HGA) and redox flexibility during TDE are observed for Ru-MOFs, while with increasing Rh content reduction towards Rh⁰ (nanoparticle formation) becomes relevant.

Investigation of the catalytic ethene dimerization as test reaction peaked in a fourfold activity increase of TDE-Ru^{II,III}-HKUST-1 compared to the best result previously reported for TDE-Ru^{II,III}-HKUST-1.⁵⁶

From our data we deduce the suggestion to take advantage of the comparably high kinetic and, in particular thermal stability of PGM-MOFs. We highlight careful in-situ monitored thermal defect-engineering as a tool to tailor the defect structure quantitatively and reproducibly and thus to modulate the catalytic properties of the materials. There should be much room for design and tailoring PGM-MOFs and their TDE derivatives much beyond the scope of this conceptual study.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Experimental details, syntheses and utilized analytic devices and tools, additional XRD, sorption, EA, TGA-MS, FT-IR, Raman, computational results and catalytic data. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BDC, benzene dicarboxylate; BET, *Brunauer-Emmett-Teller*; BTC, benzene tricarboxylate; CSA, controlled secondary building-unit approach; DE, defect-engineering; DFT, density functional theory; EA, elemental analysis; EDX, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy; EoA, Energy of adsorption; ESI, electronic supporting information; FTIR, Fourier-transformed infrared (spectroscopy); HGA, hydride generating ability; HKUST, Hong-Kong University of Science and Technology; MOF, metal-organic framework; MS, mass spectrometry; NP, nanoparticle; PSD, pore size distribution; PW, paddlewheel; PXRD, powder X-ray diffraction; SLIR, surface-ligand IR spectroscopy; TA, thermal annealing; TDE, thermal defect-engineering; TGA, thermogravimetric analysis; TOF, turn over frequency; UHV, ultra-high vacuum, VT, variable temperature.

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